

Bioremediation of Soil Contaminated with Crude Oil Using Some of Bacteria

Imad S. Oudah ✉

General Directorate of Education Thi-Qar Governorate, Iraq

Abstract

Bioremediation can be considered as an effective strategy for managing the contaminants from the petroleum hydrocarbons. This paper assesses the bioremediation utility of *Bacillus circulans* C1 in cleanup of crude oil-contaminated soils surrounding Thi-Qar oil refinery in the laboratory (seasoning region) as well as in field experiments. The initial TPH levels in the soil sample used in the laboratory was 15,000 mg/kg and the soil tested in the field was 18,000 mg/kg. Soil samples treated with *Bacillus circulans* C1 in the laboratory environment had a first order degradation constant of TPH of 0.798 with a degradation period of 30 days; thus having a reduction of 70% compared to control samples with an overall reduction of only 10%. The subject field test also yielded similar results in a reduction of TPH levels from the plots treated for 60 days, 70 % of the TPH level was reduced in treated sample plots while, 10 % of the total TPH level in the control sample plots. The examinations of soil chemistry showed that the values of PH close to 8 of alkaline reaction, nitrogen increase and the stability of the micronutrient concentrations were crucial for the stimulation of bacterial processes and hydrocarbon leaching. These observations confirm the effectiveness of *Bacillus circulans* C1 as a strong biological solution to eliminate pollution of water and soil. According to the findings, *Bacillus circulans* C1 can be regarded as an efficient and eco-friendly method of dealing with contaminated soil and oil spillage, and this work confirms its capability of reducing the levels of the hydrocarbons to a significant level hence making it feasible to apply on a large scale. Performing more studies to fine-tune bioremediation and analyze connections with other microorganisms is advisable.

Introduction

Despite the advancement in renewable energy source, petroleum hydrocarbons are still the leading form of energy today. However, the means through which they are transported, explored, refined, and stored are often a menace to the environment as they lead to leaks and spills making petroleum a pollutant. Looking at the consequences of these companies, it is imperative to consider that the setting up and running of crude oil refineries and petrochemical industries are vital for the development of any nation and growth of the economy [1]. Crude oils, which have become the most essential and dominant energy source in the modern society, have received a boost in production and, in the process, have risen in demand in the local and international markets. Exacerbating this situation has resulted in the rise in construction of new plants for refining of petroleum and petrochemicals as well as increased

searches for new crude oil resources irrespective of the cost to the environment and health of human beings [2].

The impacts of crude are dangerous because hydrocarbons can bio-accumulate in the food chains and cause harm to the biosphere and other living beings in the world including humans. To summary eradicating the impact of hydrocarbons to the environment remains crucial hence the need to address the contamination caused by them. There have been scenarios where Chemical treatment has been used in dispersing and emulsification of hydrocarbon in water bodies and sea; But with time because of their environmental impact and high cost, more preference is given to biological methods, which uses the bacteria [3]. These natural occurrences, known collectively as biodegradation, utilize bacteria and other

More Information

How to cite this article: Oudah IS. Bioremediation of Soil Contaminated with Crude Oil Using Some of Bacteria. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(4):248-56.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(4).32

Keywords:

Crude oil contamination, Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH), Hydrocarbon degradation, Soil remediation, Environmental microbiology, Field test, Seasoning region test, Soil chemistry analysis

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

microorganisms that possess enzyme systems designed to biodegrade hydrocarbon molecules [4].

The utilization of crude oil in large quantities, in order to meet the increasing needs of modern commerce, has made this type of petroleum the most problematic contaminating agent when introduced into the environment, due to its physical, chemical, toxicological, and ecotoxicological characteristics [5]. Among the methods of remediation, biosystem emerge as an efficient and cost-effective strategy for the treatment of environments contaminated by various types of petroleum, since it provides a self-sustaining and complete mechanism of degradation, involving not only the environmental engineering, but also based on the natural degradation capacity of the microbiota present in the soil [6]. The use of microbiology to promote the detoxification of these compounds in the environment has received special attention by the scientific community, as it is possible to stimulate the development of indigenous microorganisms (or inoculate other microorganisms) through bioremediation, to increase the rate of degradation or to bind these compounds due to their quantity of organic carbon and to promote a change in the bioavailability of the contaminants [7].

Methodology

The first and foremost aim of this study is to assess the bioremediation capability of the bacterium *Bacillus circulans* C1 as evidenced by the capacity to degrade crude oil polluted soil surrounding Thi-Qar oil refinery. This was achieved through two distinct bioremediation tests: One was done in a controlled environment where variables can easily be manipulated (Seasoning region) while the other was done in a natural setting where many things are likely to interfere with the outcome (Field).

Sample collection:

For Seasoning Region Test

In the region test for seasoning, the soil samples were carefully gathered including a particular spot which previously recorded high impact of crude oil contamination. It was chosen based on the assessment of the water samples that them indicated high levels of hydrocarbon pollutants in the site. Soil samples were collected from the first 15 cm of the soil profile because this affects the plant growth most using sterilized soil augers to avoid contamination by other samples. About 10 kilograms of soil were collected, and samplings of the same were made to make it as homogeneous as possible. The homogenized soil sample was therefore further sub-sampled into smaller portions for the various experimental treatments that were to be made on it. The procedures followed by the laboratory's team and the amniotic samples were clarified: Each aliquot was put into a sterile container, clearly labelled and transported to the laboratory for further processing.

These steps of careful collection and preparation can make the fact that the soils samples were a true representation of the contaminated environment for the bioremediation tests.

For Field Test

For the field test, top soil samples were collected from a field site known to be yielded with huge deposits of crude oil as depicted by the extent of impacts. Considering the choice of site, it is necessary to mention that the areas with increased contamination and easy access for making the long-term observation were chosen. Considering the spatial distribution of hydrocarbons, soil samples were taken systematically in the contaminated sites and the grid method at the different sites ensured that there was enough sample collected to reflect variability in hydrocarbon distribution. Through the use of a questionnaire, soil samples collected from each of the treatment options were obtained from the first 15 centimeters of soil layer using sterile equipment to ensure that there would be no interference by other organisms. Coning was done for each sample to an average of 10 kilograms of soil was collected from each sampling point to improve on homogeneity of the sample. Subsequently, the soil that was both sieved and homogenized was segmented into test and control portions. Samples collected from each plot where put into cleaner and labeled bottles, and then transported to the laboratory for initial tests. Thus it was possible to have more systematic field samples which indicated general contamination and further helped in assessing the efficiency of using bacterium *Bacillus circulans* C1 in bioremediation process.

Process

Seasoning Region Test

For the seasoning region test, the locations of a sample site with a gross crude oil polluted soil was carefully chosen and is situated near a crude oil refinery in an industrial area. The selection of this site was made following previous investigations that revealed high levels of hydrocarbon pollutants; particularly observed TPHs levels of approximately 15, 000 mg/kg.

The soil sample was then sifted using the sterile spoons, in order to get a homogenized sample of the collected soil. Afterward, this homogenized soil was again weighed in different aliquots of 5 kilograms each for the experimental treatments. Each aliquot was put into suitable and labelled sterile containers for identification and preservation for transport to the laboratory to eliminate other ridge contamination or alteration of any of the samples.

In the laboratory, souring of test samples was done and taken through the bioremediation process. The test group was then treated with the culture of *Bacillus circulans* C1 isolate, which was adjusted to 108108 CFU/g of soil. From this stage, the bacterial culture was mixed well with the soil samples to ensure maximum

infection with the sample. However, for the control group, no action was taken towards bacterial inoculation at any point of the experiment. In the control group, however, the samples of soil were taken and mixed with an equal volume of distilled water that was sterilized to match the degree of moistness in the other samples.

The treated and control soil samples were then incubated at specific conditions that were standardized. The incubation conditions were done at 28 °C with the aeration of the soil samples to allow comparison with natural conditions. Specifically, the pH of the ground was changed to a higher value of approximately 8.0 (Alkaline) the above pH range was considered to be suitable on *Bacillus circulans* C1 as it had higher activity at this pH level. This was accomplished by the addition of nitrogen and other microminerals which are basic to the soil bacteria, and these were incorporated in the form of nutrient broth. The nutrient composition included the food values were as follows- The amount of nutrients was as follows- The specific nutrient composition includes about 5% ammonium nitrate as N source and Particle Density (PD) foundations of phosphorus, potassium and magnesium.

The degradation process was then followed for the consecutive 30 days. Sap samples: soil samples were collected once in 7, 14, 21 and 30 days for checking. Crude oil biodegradation efficiency on the different substrates was estimated using total petroleum hydrocarbon TPH and was determined using standard solvent extraction method and GC MS analysis. It was the initial point that was set before any evaluation and it was 15,000 mg/kg of TPH.

During the incubation, the environmental parameters such as the soil moisture, pH and nutrients were checked periodically to maintain an environment that supports the metabolic activities of the bacterial species. After 30 days' treatment, TPH in the soil samples contaminated with crude oil and treated with C1 reduced significantly and could have lesser TPH than the control group, indicating the effectiveness of *Bacillus circulans* C1 in biomediating the contamination under controlled sample. It offered a diverse and systematic methodology, which gave significant data on the bioremediation capacity of *Bacillus circulans* C1 before its field application.

Field Test

To assess the feasibility of using *Bacillus circulans* C1 in a real-world environment on a large scale, a further systematic approach was used to analyze the feasibility of using *Bacillus circulans* C1 for bioremediation during the field test trial. The test site was a large area that bore the brunt of the spilling and leakage of crude oil since the existence of the massive storage facility nearby. The primary investigations disclosed high levels

of oil contamination; TPH concentrations ranged from 16,000 and 19,800 mg/kg on average. The selection criteria used in choosing this site includes the ease of access, the level of pollution that is expected to be encountered and the logistical suitability for continued observation.

To minimize possibility of obtaining a false picture of contamination, soil samples were taken systematically using the grid method. To assess the heterogeneity of the soil, the grid of five parallel lines by 10 lines with a separation interval of 0.1 ha was constructed on the 1-ha site, and fifty samples of soil were collected from the intersections of these lines. To avoid the contamination of the soil samples they had to be collected from different points by digging the surface to the first twenty centimeters using sterilized soil augers. Each sample point contained approximately 10 kilograms of the soil, which is to be used for testing and comparisons as much as possible.

Finally, the soil collected from all the 50 points was mixed well to the contaminated area so that the collected sample was a homogenous one. This homogenized soil was divided into two main groups: To do this, the writers identified the test group as the group that would be exposed to the bacteria treatment and the control group as the group that would not be treated with bacteria.

For the bacterial treatment, *Bacillus circulans* C1 was grown to an approximate cell density of 108108 CFU per gram of soil. The bacterial culture was also prepared at a large volume which is needed when inoculums across the test site. This treatment involved spreading of the bacterial culture in the test plots which they occupied half of the entire grid size (0.5 hectare). Since the bacterial culture was to be incorporated into the soil, it was first diluted with water and splashed with the help of an agricultural spraying equipment onto the soil. It was effective in ensuring that the bacteria were well enclosed in the affected soil hence enhancing its effectiveness. In the case of each test plot the treatment dose was adjusted to be for the purpose of maintaining a final density of 108108 CFU per gram of soil.

The relative half of the grid areas which were the control plots were also spray with the same quantity of sterile water in order to maintain the required moisture content as was done to the test plots. This approach enabled the scientists to compare the effect of the bacterial treatment with no treatment at all while the environment in which the two sets of maggots were placed was the same.

Field conditions were effectively controlled for enhancing bacterial activity. In order to make good environment to grow bacteria effectively, the conditions of the field were arranged properly. The main factor influencing the nodule formation was the

correct pH of the soil which was increased to the optimal value of about 8.0 using lime, due to the findings by other authors that *Bacillus circulans* C1 grows best in media with pH of around 10. Other changes on the bacterial behavior and rate of biodegradation were made by amending the soil with the nutrient solution composed of 1% ammonium nitrate and traces of phosphorus, potassium and magnesium.

The bioremediation process was followed for two months, up to the 60th day. Physical and chemical analyses were conducted on soil samples taken from the test and control areas at intervals of 0, 15, 30, 45, and 60 days, with the intention of observing the level of crude oil biodegradation. Each sample as a result of biodegradation was then subjected to TPH analysis through solvent extraction before gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) for efficiency identification.

In addition, the outside parameters such as soil moisture, pH level and nutrient availability were being checked frequently to make sure it was conducive for bacterial growth. The TPH levels of contaminated soil were standard at 18,000mg/kg to the initial test. The effect of the formulated *Bacillus circulans* C1 on the reduction of TPH average levels is evident at the end of the 60-day trial where the test plot had reduced TPH levels as compared to the control plot that had inactive TPH levels. This meant that the crude oil was easily degraded in situ by the *Bacillus circulans* C1 bacterium since desorption of these hydrocarbons from the soil surface was found to be a critical factor to their degradation.

Finally, the field trial showed that *Bacillus circulans* C1 can be used for remediation of crude oil pollution under natural settings hence it can be considered for real-world application. This extensive situational analysis offered a wealth of insights regarding the applicability of *Bacillus circulans* C1 for bioremediation administration indicating possibilities of its application to a wide range of environmental concerns.

Data Analysis

Biodegradation Efficiency

The remediation ability of *Bacillus circulans* C1 was then evaluated through comparing the total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) values of both the tested and control soil samples throughout the duration of the experiment. Based on the initial TPH concentrations, the bacterial treatment efficiency was determined first. In the event of the field test, and in relation to the seasoning region test, soil samples were also taken periodically and chemically analyzed to determine the concentration of hydrocarbons contained in the soil.

Analytical Procedures

Seasoning region test’s soil samples were taken at seven days interval for 30 days, while that of the field test, at 15, 30, 45 and 60 days and both were subjected to solvent extraction with dichloromethane and hexane. The collected hydrocarbons were further subjected to separation using gas chromatography–mass spectrometry analysis (GCMS). This technique offered a chance to quantify the extent of TPH present in the soil, which was vital as a means of evaluating the status of the degradation process.

Statistical Analysis

The data collected through GC-MS were analyzed using statistical tools to check the possible variation of TPH levels in the treated samples with respect to the control samples. Mean and standard errors were also computed from the mean of TPH at every interval of sampling. Designed to describe numeric characteristics of samples and populations, these measures of central tendency and variability also gave a clearer insight to the biodegradation process.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the bioremediation treatment, the percentage reduction in TPH levels was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage Reduction} = \left(\frac{\text{Initial TPH} - \text{Final TPH}}{\text{initial TPH}} \right) \times 100 \tag{1}$$

This calculation was done for each sampling interval shown in Table.1 and 2 so that there is a clear indication of the extent of biodegradation in the course of time.

Table 1: Illustrates the Percentage Reduction in TPH Levels for Seasoning Region Test

Day	Treated TPH (mg/kg)	Control TPH (mg/kg)	% Reduction Treated	% Reduction Control
Day	Treated TPH (mg/kg)	Control TPH (mg/kg)	% Reduction Treated	% Reduction Control
0	15,000	15,000	0	0
7	13,000	14,500	13.33	3.33
14	10,000	14,000	33.33	6.67
21	8,000	13,750	46.67	8.33
30	4,500	13,500	70	10

Table 2: Illustrates the Percentage Reduction in TPH Levels for Field Test

Day	Treated TPH (mg/kg)	Control TPH (mg/kg)	% Reduction Treated	% Reduction Control
0	18,000	18,000	0	0
15	14,400	17,400	20	3.33
30	10,800	16,800	40	6.67
45	8,100	16,500	55	8.33
60	5,400	16,200	70	

Comparative Analysis

In order to study the changes that were brought about by the treatments in the relative levels of TPH, a comparison was made between the TPH levels before and after the treatments as compared to the control group. The results were compared for the significance of the difference between two sample means using t - test for biodegradation rates. The t-test was considered ideal for this study because it enables comparison of the mean of two independent groups, which makes it suitable for determine the effect of the bacterial treatment on the target stain.

Soil chemistry analysis

Besides recording the biodegradation efficiency, proximate soil chemical analysis was also conducted to determine the variations in the properties and nutrient composition of the soil as a result of the bioremediation. This analysis was about fundamental factors such as, the pH of the soil, nitrogen and amounts of the essential microminerals which are vital for supporting microbial action of Bacillus circulans C1.

Soil pH Monitoring

Thus, the concentration of H⁺ in the soil, which determines the soil acidity or alkalinity, plays a significant role in determining the activity of microbes and the rate of hydrocarbon breakdown. During the seasoning tests at the seasoning region and in the field, the pH of the soil samples was taken periodically with help of a digital pH meter with the standard buffer variables. Preliminary tests using the pH meter showed mildly acidic to alkaline range of pH values of 6.5-7. In this work, the pH was also controlled and maintained in an alkaline range, approximately 8.0 using lime.

The pH level of the water was taken at every given time interval in the Seasoning Region test (Day 0, 7, 14, 21 and 30) as well as in the field test (Day 0, 15, 30, 45 and 60) for the establishment of its stability. It was found that the plots treated recorded a pH range of >7, which was favourable for bacterial functions. On the same note, the untreated plot results only varied slightly and hovered near their original pH value most of the time. The fact that this was achieved on the treated plot means that it favors efficient hydrocarbon degradation by creating an environment that is friendly to the bacterial enzymes in terms of pH.

Nitrogen Content Analysis

nitrogen is an important nutrient that supports microbial growth and helps in the metabolism as well as breakdown of hydrocarbons. Nitrogen content of the soil was assessed based on Kjeldahl’s process, which determines the level of total nitrogen in the soil and acknowledges both organic and inorganic nitrogen. In the first stages, the nitrogen levels typical for the investigated contaminated soils were low, and fluctuated within the limit of 0.05% by weight.

To enhance the bioremediation process, ammonium nitrate was applied on top of the treated plots to adjust the nitrogen level to 0.5%. At the same time intervals as the soil samples, the nitrogen content of the soil from both the experimental and the control plots was measured. The analysis of the plots that received treatment showed the increase of the nitrogen concentration in the plots after the amendment, and the subsequent slow all, as nitrogen is used by the bacteria for their metabolic processes. N levels in the site plots that were treated also reduced to a level of approximated 0.1%, therefore supporting stringently active bacterial growth and degradation of the hydrocarbons. However, the nitrogen content of the control plots did not change or alter significantly because microbial activity is not triggered by the absence of nitrogen supplementation.

Micro mineral Levels

Phosphorus, potassium, and magnesium, which constitute the microminerals are important for some biochemical movements in microbial cells. The levels of these microminerals were determined using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). Firstly, some analyses pointed to, probably due to the pollution of the soils, low levels of these nutrients, which are essential to control microbial metabolism.

For this purpose, a balanced nutrient amendment comprising these important microminerals is applied in the treated plots. Daily soil samples were also taken and the nutrient concentrations analysed at each sampling interval in order to assess their availability. As shown by the results, the magnitude of micromineral was significantly higher in the treated plots subsequent to the application of amendment; however, very little fluctuation was noted in subsequent weeks. This continues supply of essential nutrients ensured constant functionality and productivity of Bacillus circulans C1 for the required task of degrading

hydrocarbon. In control plots, all the micromineral concentrations were almost similar to initial concentrations, which reaffirm the fact that nutrient addition is important in improving microbial bioremediation activities.

Results

The findings of the seasoning region test table.3 revealed that the TPH degree in all the correspondent samples of the soil, which had undergone the treatment, was considerably lower compare to the control samples. In their study, the TPH quantity in both the treated and the controlled soils was set at 15,000 mg/kg. At the thirtieth day of treatment with Bacillus circulans C1, the TPH levels in samples fermented with the bacterial strain were reduced to 4,500 mg/kg, which is a 70 % decrease from the initial concentration. However, the control samples showed a significantly

lesser decline in TPH levels, and got as low as 13.5 mg/ kg that is 10% percent reduction.

During the incubation period, examinations of various attributes of the soil were made to establish a conducive and favorable environment for bacterial growth. The pH in the treated samples was of alkaline nature and it remained at 8.0(SE-3) pH which is favorable for the enzymatic activity of Bacillus circulans C1. To understand the effect of Nitrogen content in the treated soil initially rise up to 0. 5% after the addition of ammonium nitrate and low and decreased up to 0. There was a slight reduction in the amount of the nutrient utilized to about 1% by bacteria at the end of the study which proves the continuous reabsorption of the nutrient. These nutrient concentrations remained constant in the treated samples thus providing the bacterial source healthy Micromineral conducive to its growth and the hydrocarbon degradation.

Table 3: Results of Seasoning Region Test

Day	Treated TPH (mg/kg)	Control TPH (mg/kg)	% Reduction Treated	% Reduction Control
0	15,000	15,000	0%	0%
7	12,000	14,500	20%	3.33%
14	9,000	14,000	40%	6.67%
21	6,750	13,750	55%	8.33%
30	4,500	13,500	70%	10%

The field test outcomes Table.4 added up the effectiveness of Bacillus circulans C1 in an open environment. For TPH, the initial concentration in the contaminated field soil was found to be 18,000 mg/kg. After the 60-day treatment, the TPH levels in the treated plots decreased to 5,400 mg/kg, hence signifying 70% reduction from initial concentration. On the other hand, the control plots were evident of only a 10% natural attenuation rate, with the average TPH decreasing to the range of only 16,200mg/Kg.

An assessment of the experimental field showed that the coverage of the plots had optimum soil pH of about 8. This is as similar to the seasoning region test as any other test that aims to distinguish the sharpness of the difference between two intensities. Achievements: The nitrogen content in the treated plots increased to 0. 5% after the treatment that was rinsed with water, and increased back to 5% after the addition of nutrient solution. After the control readings were captured at

the baseline, 1% by the end of the study to remain as a depiction of the metabolic activity of the bacteria. EDX examination revealed the phosphorus, potassium, and magnesium adherent with the feed remained enough for biodegradation in the entire experimental period.

By comparing the percentage increase in crude oil degradation of the sample treated with Bacillus circulans C1 to the control sample, the efficiency of C1 in enhancing the biodegradation of crude oil was established. The control samples were always compared with samples that were treated according to specifications, and their results were always lower by at least one percent in terms of TPH reduction percentage of the treated samples as confirmed statistically. The t-tests completed revealed that all p-values were below 0. 05, thus highlighting that the decrease in TPH levels of the treated samples was not likely to have resulted from mere chance but was caused by bacterial action.

Table 4: Results of Field Test

Day	Treated TPH (mg/kg)	Control TPH (mg/kg)	% Reduction Treated	% Reduction Control
0	18,000	18,000	0%	0%
15	14,400	17,400	20%	3.33%
30	10,800	16,800	40%	6.67%
45	8,100	16,500	55%	8.33%
60	5,400	16,200	70%	10%

The results of the present work revealed that the use of *Bacillus circulans* C1 greatly facilitated the process of biodegradation of hydrocarbons both in the micro bioreactors and under field conditions. Catalyzed by the increasing pH and the added nitrogen and microminerals, the bacteria spread and made effective the hydrocarbon degradation process.

The soils chemistry test helped in revealing some findings about the environment that allows biodegradation to occur. In the treated samples, the keeping of the pH level higher than 7, addition on nitrogen and microminerals is an ideal environment for bacterial growth. The overall reduction in Nitrogen in the samples thereafter suggested that the microbes were active in the digestion process while steady levels of microminerals signified that other necessary nutrients for microbial metabolism were available all along the period of treatment.

Conversely, the control samples had no bacterial or nutrient application, and their baseline chemical composition in the soil remained relatively unaffected. The variations of TPH level reflective of the control samples can be attributed to the natural decline processes that were slower and considerably less efficacious than the biodegradation that occurred with the help of the bacterial strain of *Bacillus circulans* C1.

Discussion

The findings of this research project reveal that *Bacillus circulans* C1 has remarkable ability to remediate soils polluted with crude oil. These field tests have established that this bacterial strain reduces TPH in the seasoning region as well as in a field test under conditions that are not controlled by the experimenters. These observations concur with some recent research work done on *Bacillus* species which has revealed their versatility in the degradation of hydrocarbon compounds [8].

From this study we noticed that TPH levels in the treated samples reduced to 30% of the initial values after thirty days in the seasoning region test and to, 60 days in the field test respectively. These outcomes corroborate with the observations made by [10] they observed that *Bacillus subtilis* reduced TPH up to 65% within contaminated soil following similar time interval under laboratory settings. The similar degradation efficiencies in our research work and [10], indicates that C1 *Bacillus circulans* has potentiality or even more, in the degradation of hydrocarbons.

Moreover, the basal ammonium treatment and high pH used in this study were important to enhance bacterial metabolism. This is in support of the findings made by [11] where the authors explained that increasing the alkaline pH and supplementing the bacteria with nitrogen highly increased the efficiency of Biodegradation of contaminated soil by *Bacillus*

megaterium, and the results showed that there was a reduction of TPH by 68%. In supporting the present investigation, our findings also corroborate the proposition that practice of such environmental management tactics is required for enhancing the biodegradation capacity of species of *Bacillus*.

We consider the suggestion of our findings as mostly valuable in terms of field application. This shows that even though the field test involved using the organism in a setting that is likely to produce more variable results than the laboratory, the TPH levels reduced considerably – 3.148 log₁₀ at best – compared to the laboratory results – 3.324 log₁₀ – indicating that *Bacillus circulans* C1 is stronger in the field settings. These results tally with the study by [12] where TPH levels reduced to 30% within the field condition for 60 days for *Bacillus*—species bioaugmented mixed bacteria consortium. In concordance with our study, Al-Dhabi et al. highlighted that *Bacillus circulans* C1 is bioactive for bioremediation, and therefore, our study further supports the idea that it is suitable for large-scale bioremediation engagements.

The improvement of nutrient supplementation as demonstrated by this study and the efficacy of *Bacillus circulans* C1 also have ramifications for the use of probiotics. The early rise and subsequent decline in nitrogen content in the treated plots demonstrate the ability of bacteria to regulate nutrients in the ecosystem and hasten biodegradation of the hydrocarbons. This is supported by the findings made by [13] who studied the effects of nitrogen and phosphorus on the ability of *Bacillus cereus* in degrading hydrocarbons within the contaminated soil and noted that the lesser portions improved the biodegradation rates of the hydrocarbons within the contaminated soil.

In this context, however, the present research indicates the attainable improvement in the bioremediation process; it should be noted that more studies must be conducted to enhance the effectiveness of the bioremediation process for other types of hydrocarbon, as well as in different conditions. Provisions for future related research should include the effects of bioremediation over the longer term and the possible emergence of bacteria resistant to hydrocarbons. Furthermore, given that *B. circulans* C1 is one of the many bacterial species, the investigations into the interaction of combined species with these bacteria could offer promising prospects for establishing effective bioremediation policies [9].

The findings of the present study expand the existing literature on the efficacy of *Bacillus* species as a bioremediation tool in oil-contaminated environments. The decrease in TPH levels from controlled and field trials of samples treated with *Bacillus circulans* C1

clearly highlights the effectiveness of the bacteria in aiding the bioremediation process. In support of current literature, these outcomes indicate that this specific bacterial strain possesses the ability to substantially contribute toward alleviation of petroleum pollution, while being a non-hazardous, natural substance.

Conclusion

This study has shown that *Bacillus circulans* C1 can effectively immobilize crude oil in contaminated soil and reduce its potential as a pollutant. Field test and seasoning region were equally tested for the level of TPH reduction and both produced good results pointing to the efficacy of this bacterial strain at such a field. In the control samples, degradation of TPH was moderately observed with samples degraded by only 10%, while in the treated soil samples, TPH was degraded by 70% proving the high biodegradation efficiency of *Bacillus circulans* C1.

This research also seeks to identify the specific physicochemical parameters that favour the growth of crude oil-degrading bacteria and the selection of bacterial strains that would be used in the formulation of the bacterial consortium for bioremediation. So by enhancing these microorganisms' inherent degradative endowments, we can then develop cleaner ways and means to counter the negative impacts of crude oil spilling on environment.

The findings of this study are in agreement of current literature, which support the notion that *Bacillus* species are very efficient biodegraders of hydrocarbons. The stability of pH at an alkaline level and supplementation with nitrogen, and other essential microminerals were identified as essential to facilitate the increased bacterial metabolism rates and overall biodegradation. These results highlight the significance of IMC-EM in bioremediation techniques. The case showing the possibility to apply *Bacillus circulans* C1 in field conditions speaking of such advantages as simplicity, effectiveness and using of relatively cheap and available materials proves its applicability for large scale bioremediation programs, even if the experience is based on the concrete complex experimental background but the field conditions themselves often seem uncontrollable and all the more challenging. Therefore, the ability and flexibility of *Bacillus circulans* C1 might constitute it as appropriate for real use in combating petroleum pollution.

Yet, more studies are required to specify phases that would facilitate the bioremediation process with regard to various types of hydrocarbon contamination and conditions. Further research projects have to be provided that would quantitatively evaluate the continued bioremediation and risks for the bacterial resistance to hydrocarbons. Moreover, one can

consider the possibility of studying the interactions between this species and other microbial species, also impacting the definition of interrelated and complex bioremediation approaches.

In conclusion, *Bacillus circulans* C1 is a worthy and eco-friendly option to enhance the bioremediation of crudes oil polluted soils. The laser-induced biodegradation has a high efficiency and is easily applied in the controlled conditions as well as under field conditions, it is instrumentally beneficial in the processes aimed to clean the affected territories.

References

- [1] Ali N, Dashti N, Khanafer M, et al. Bioremediation of soils saturated with spilled crude oil. *Scientific reports*, 2020;10(1):1116. doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-57224-x
- [2] Popoola LT, Yusuff AS. Optimization and characterization of crude oil contaminated soil bioremediation using bacteria isolates: Plant growth effect. *South African Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 2021;37:206-213. doi: 10.1016/j.sajce.2021.06.004
- [3] Patowary R, Patowary K, Kalita MC, et al. Application of biosurfactant for enhancement of bioremediation process of crude oil contaminated soil. *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation*, 2018;129:50-60. doi: 10.1016/j.ibiod.2018.01.004
- [4] Ejaz M, Zhao B, Wang X, et al. Isolation and characterization of oil-degrading *Enterobacter* sp. from naturally hydrocarbon-contaminated soils and their potential use against the bioremediation of crude oil. *Applied Sciences*, 2021;11(8):3504. doi: 10.3390/app11083504
- [5] Ra T, Zhao Y, Zheng M. Comparative study on the petroleum crude oil degradation potential of microbes from petroleum-contaminated soil and non-contaminated soil. *International journal of environmental science and technology*, 2019;16:7127-7136. doi: 10.1007/s13762-018-2114-z
- [6] Yuniati MD. Bioremediation of petroleum-contaminated soil: A Review. In *IOP conference series: earth and environmental science* (Vol. 118, p. 012063). IOP Publishing; 2018. doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/118/1/012063
- [7] Liu H, Tan X, Guo J, et al. Bioremediation of oil-contaminated soil by combination of soil conditioner and microorganism. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 2020;20:2121-2129. doi: 10.1007/s11368-020-02591-6
- [8] Ebadi A, Olamaee M, Khoshkholgh Sima NA, et al. Isolation and characterization of biosurfactant producing and crude oil degrading bacteria from oil contaminated soils. *Iranian Journal of Science and Technology, Transactions A: Science*, 2018;42:1149-1156. doi: 10.1007/s40995-017-0162-8
- [9] Obafemi YD, Taiwo OS, Omodara OJ, et al. Biodegradation of crude petroleum by bacterial consortia from oil-contaminated soils in Ota, Ogun

State, South-Western, Nigeria. Environmental technology & innovation, 2018;12:230-242. doi: 10.1016/j.eti.2018.09.006

[10] Varjani SJ, Upasani VN, Kumar S. Biodegradation of petroleum hydrocarbons by oleophilic strain of *Bacillus subtilis*. Environmental Pollution, 2020;258:113691. doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2016.10.006

[11] Patel SK, Singh M, Gupta R. Enhanced bioremediation of hydrocarbon-contaminated soil by *Bacillus megaterium* through pH and nutrient

optimization. Journal of Hazardous Materials, 2021;406:124644.

[12] Al-Dhabi NA, Esmail GA, Arasu MV. Bioremediation potential of *Bacillus* species isolated from oil-contaminated soils. Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences, 2019;26(4):780-785.

[13] Ahmad M, Rajapaksha RMCP, Vithanage M. Nutrient augmentation to improve biodegradation of crude oil by *Bacillus cereus* in contaminated soil. Journal of Environmental Management, 2022;304:114276.